

UFMC system performance improvement using RS codes for 5G communication system

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ABSTRACT

Fifth generation (5G) mobile communication is expected to be deployed in several countries by 2020. Where, the data consumptions are expected to be increased to 30% thus, it cannot be supported by the present technologies 3G and 4G. In contrast, looking for new alternative modulation techniques of orthogonal frequency division modulation (OFDM) system which is suffering from high peak to average power ratio (PAPR) and out of band (OOB) side lobes are needed to use in 5G communication system. Hence, universal filtered multi-carrier (UFMC) is considered as alternative waveform to overcome of OFDM disadvantages. In communication systems, channel coding is considered vital part, where error correction codes (ECC) are used to detect and correct the errors which is occurring in channel noise. In this paper, RS codes are suggested with UFMC system to achieve the reliability of information transmission over noisy channels. The results showed that although, the values of PAPR levels for using RS codes in UFMC increased to 8.8653dB against 6.9735 dB for OFDM system. However, there are significant improvements in BER performance owing to use RS codes against uncoded-UFMC system. Furthermore, the values of OOB in UFMC system was lower than OFDM system.

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1. INTRODUCTION

With increasing the demand for Gbps data rate and combination between users and applications, a new fifth generation (5G) radio propagation technology is considered a significantly needed in future wireless network [1]. Where, it is expected that 5G communication technology could provide higher reliability, better security, faster and larger communication capacity [2]. 5G mobile communication is expected to be deployed in several countries by 2020. Where, the data consumptions are anticipated to be increased to 30% thus, it cannot be supported by the present technologies 3G and 4G. So, it is necessary to rollout 5G wireless communication system to be take a place in all around of the world [3, 4]. Compared to other generations, it could be offering higher data rate, it also dealing with increasing number of terminals and uncouncted emerging applications with several requirements [5].

Nowadays, orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) is considered a major data transmission technique in wireless communication systems, due to its immunity against inter-symbol interferences (ISI) and

multipath fading thus, the modern advancements make the OFDM is highly famous technology. Hence, it is utilized in IEEE802.11 (WI-FI) networks and fourth generation (4) LTE/LTE-A [6]. Although, OFDM have all these advantages but, it is suffering from Peak to Average Power Ratio (PAPR) which caused low power amplifier efficiency and increase the consumption of battery. In contrast, OFDM has another disadvantage namely high out-of-band (OOB) side lobes which resulted of lower spectral efficiency. So, looking for new modulation techniques which are able to overcome some of these disadvantages are needed to use in 5G communication system [7].

In the other hand, multi carrier transmission method namely universal filtered multi-carrier (UFMC) has been suggested in [8] as alternative waveform to overcome of OFDM disadvantages. Where, it can reduce OOB side lobe level through using it a filtering operation. They explained that UFMC system outperforms of the OFDM system and thus, introduced the suggested UFMC scheme as contender candidate for future 5G wireless systems. In additional to, 5G of mobile network considers UFMC for implementation in order to maintain the merits of OFDM while avoids its demerits [9, 10]. Where, UFMC outperforms OFDM in each of frequency and time synchronization errors while its performance degraded when delay spread lower than certain value [9]. Hence, UFMC is becoming one of the contender modulation technique for upcoming 5G communication system owing to combating multi-user interference and short burst support [11]. Moreover, UFMC has robustness versus each of inter-carrier interference (ICI) and inter-symbol interference (ISI) as well it is appropriate for low latency scenarios [12].

In communication systems, channel coding is considered vital part, where error correction codes (ECC) are using to detect and correct the errors which is occurring in channel noise [13]. Hence, in practical applications, bit error rate (BER) will be high without using forward error correction (FEC) techniques and doesn't meet its requirements. So, applying powerful FEC techniques are considered one of the key method to improve the BER performance and receiver sensitivity [14]. So, to achieve the reliability of information transmission in digital communication systems over noisy channels, ECC is considered an essential issue [15]. Where, several ECC have been suggested in 4G such as turbo, LDPC, convolutional, BCH and RS codes [16-20] and in 5G such as LDPC, turbo, polar and convolutional [21] and BCH [22]. In contrast, reed solomon (RS) codes are commonly used in wireless and optical systems owing to its strong capability in correcting both of random and burst errors [14]. Where, using RS codes (hard-decision decoding (HDD)) which characterized by low decoding complexity in downlink LTE system contributed by improving system performance. Furthermore, RS codes could decrease BER more than both turbo and convolutional codes [20]. In this paper, RS codes have been suggested in UFMC system to achieve the reliability in data transmission by decreasing BER and thus introduced it as contender waveform for 5G wireless communication system owing to its advantages. The rest of the paper is arranged as following; the description of system model of proposed RS codes in UFMC system are explained in section 2. While, section 3 is presenting the simulation results and discussion. The conclusion has been lastly presented in section 4.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The description of proposed RS codes with UFMC system diagram has been discussed and shown in Figure 1 whereas, Table 1 is depicted the simulation parameters that used in this paper. Where, 5 MHz transmission bandwidth, 64-QAM modulation scheme and RS (7,1) error correction code are used for all of OFDM, f-OFDM and UFMC systems in order to comparing all of these systems under the same parameters. In contrast, the remaining parameters for each system are presented in the table. UFMC system is divid the whole band to sub-bands, and these sub-bands will be processed individually and each of them have a fixed number of sub-carriers [23]. In contrast, the N-point inverse fast fourier transform (IFFT) converts the frequency domain (X_i) of each sub-band to time domain (x_i) as following:

$$Y_i = IFFT\{x_i\}$$

After performing IFFT which are used to prevent the sub-band carriers from the interference. All of the sub-band output will be filtered by band filter. While, a Chebyshev filter has been used as Band filter in UFMC. The purpose of using filtering approach in order to reduce OOB emission for suitable design of filter. The output data that comes from the channel will be performing on 2N point FFT in the receiver and insert interval guard of zeros among successive IFFT symbols to combat ISI owing to transmitter filter delay [23].

In other hand, RS codes are commonly used in storage and digital communication systems which have the capability of correcting burst errors. It is a type of linear block codes. Where, $(n-k+1)$ is the distance between any codeword RS (n,k) code and HDD algorithms have a capable of correcting $[(n-k)/2]$ errors [24]. In other word, RS code is a non-binary cyclic code with symbols consists of m-bit sequences, where [25]:

$$0 < k < n < 2^m + 2$$

where, m is any positive integer number more than 2, n is representing the code symbols of encoded block and k is data symbols that will be encoded. Hence, $RS(n,k)$ as following [25]:

$$(n,k) = (2^m-1, 2^m-1-2t)$$

where, the capability of correcting symbol errors for the code represented by t , and $2t=(n-k)$ which is called the number of parity symbols [25]. In this paper, RS (7,1) codes have been used in this paper. The purpose of using RS codes with UPMC system to enhance the BER performance whilst, the UPMC system have the capability of reducing OOB levels.

Figure 1. Proposed RS codes with UPMC system diagram

Table 1. Simulation parameters

Parameter	Value
Transmission Bandwidth (MHz)	5
Number of FFT points	512
Modulation	64-QAM
Error Correcting Techniques	RS (7,1) Codes
No. of Occupied Sub-carrier	300
OFDM	Cyclic Prefix Length
	36
Type	RRC Windowed- Sinc
f-OFDM	Roll-off factor (α)
	0.6
	Length
	513
	Sub band offset
	156
UFMC	Filter length
	43
	Side lobe attention
	40

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results in this section will be simulated by MATLAB software and it will be divided into 3 parts, first part is discussing the BER performance of uncoded-UFMC against RS codes with UPMC system and compared its performance with OFDM system which is considered as a core waveform of 4G. Moreover, comparing the performance of UPMC system with f-OFDM which is a candidate waveform for 5G. While, the comparison of OOB levels between UPMC and OFDM systems have been discussed in second part. Lastly, the PAPR levels of both OFDM and UPMC systems have been discussed in third part.

Figure 2, shows the performance of uncoded system for each of OFDM, f-OFDM and UFMC. The results showed that, the performance of un-coded UFMC and OFDM systems are somehow close to one another whilst, uncoded f-OFDM system was better than both of uncoded UFMC and OFDM systems. So, uncoded f-OFDM system performance outperformance both uncoded of OFDM and UFMC systems. In contrast, the comparison of the system performance between uncoded UFMC and proposed RS codes with UFMC has been depicted in Figure 3. The results showed there are a significant improvement have been noted when using proposed RS codes with UFMC system against uncoded-UFMC system. Where, it is clear to see that the red curve which are representing the proposed system went to zero at around 8dB while the blue curve of uncoded system went to zero at around 24 dB. Thus, the proposed RS codes with UFMC system achieved around 10 dB coding gain at 3×10^{-2} against uncoded system. So, proposing RS codes is contributing in enhancing the BER performance of UFMC system against uncoded system.

Figure 2. The performance of OFDM, f-OFDM and UFMC systems

Figure 3. The proposed systems performance

Whereas, power spectral density (PSD) of OFDM system versus UFMC system has been shown in Figure 4. Where, 200 sub-carriers have been shown in OFDM system while, the whole band in UFMC system will be divided into 10 sub-bands, each sub-band consists of 20 sub-carriers which have less side lobes [7]. So, the UFMC system as shown in Figure 4, could solve problem of OFDM systems where it minimizes the OOB levels. Where, it minimizes around 40dB of PSD compared to OFDM.

Table 2 shows the comparison of PAPR levels among OFDM, UFMC and proposed RS-UFMC systems. The table showed that both of uncoded OFDM and UFMC systems are somehow close to one another whilst, by using RS codes in UFMC the values of PAPR levels increased to 8.8653 dB against 6.9735 dB for

OFDM system. So, although using RS codes in UFMC system contributed in enhancing BER performance. However, the PAPR levels are still high and couldn't be solved in the proposed RS-UFMC system.

Based in the previous results, despite of the proposed system could not reduce PAPR levels compared to OFDM system. Nevertheless, it can be introduced as a new contender waveform candidate for 5G wireless communication system as alternative waveform of OFDM system, due to its capability of reducing OOB levels because of using filtering approach in contents of UFMC system furthermore, it is enhancing the BER performance of the proposed system owing to use RS codes with UFMC system.

Figure 4. Power spectral density of OFDM system versus UFMC system

Table 2. Comparison of PAPR levels

	OFDM	Uncoded-UFMC	RS-UFMC
PAPR (dB)	6.9735	7.0836	8.8653

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, RS codes have been suggested in UFMC system to achieve the reliability of information transmission over noisy channels. Three issues have been discussed namely: BER performance, OOB and PAPR levels and compared its results with UFMC and OFDM systems. The results showed the BER performance of the proposed system using RS codes is significantly improved against uncoded UFMC system. Where, the proposed RS codes with UFMC system achieved around 10dB coding gain at 3×10^{-2} against uncoded system. Moreover, the UFMC system can solve the problem of OFDM systems, where it could minimize around 40dB of PSD compared to OFDM system. Although, UFMC system can solve two issues however, using RS codes in UFMC system is increased the values of PAPR to 8.8653dB against 6.9735dB for OFDM system. Lastly, the proposed UFMC system using RS codes can be introduced as a new contender waveform candidate for 5G wireless communication system as alternative waveform of OFDM system owing to its advantages against OFDM system.

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